

EDUCATION LEADERSHIP FOR INDUSTRIALIZATION IN TANZANIA

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Abstract:

The role of education leadership in relation to industrialization process and knowledge economy is very high significant in many developing countries focusing stable economy, innovation and quality education. The purpose of this paper is to discuss the connectedness among the three key words: education leadership, industrialization and knowledge economy in a framework upon which education policy makers, and other significant stakeholders can apply in enhancing education and economic development in Africa particular Tanzania and other developing countries. The recommendations provided emphasis the significance of involvement of education stakeholders in finding opportunities and resolving challenges in education system for economic and education prosperity. Education leadership from school to top levels play significant role in formulating competent base curriculum which leads to skilled human capital, innovation, production of quality goods and service.

Keywords: education leadership; industrialization; knowledge economy

1. Introduction

This paper addresses the way education leadership is responsible at all levels namely, elementary, secondary, postsecondary, universities and the entire education system to involve stakeholders and create positive change, products, image and new policies for development. The expected results of good education leadership could be manifested in the quality of education and production of skilled learners who are able to improve their lives, understand the world trends, use the available economic opportunities in the country to engage themselves in economic production including industrialization and coping with challenges as individuals and community members.

Industrialization has been explained as the process by which traditionally non-industrial sectors of an economy such as agriculture, education, and health become

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increasingly become part of the manufacturing, production and service provision sector of the economy. Definitely industrialization is the outcome of good educational leadership which nurtures quality education and useful skills. Organized industrialization has great influence in knowledge economy.

Knowledge economy is essentially an economy whose development is based on the ability to create and use knowledge, life skills and ICT which together lead to innovation development and productivity. Mass production of goods and services influences export and foreign currency income.

Therefore, this paper discusses the significance of education leadership in enhancing industrialization then knowledge economy using the experience from around the world, Africa and Tanzania. The key issue is to give full understanding of the way education leadership could enhance industrialization and knowledge economy.

2. Education leadership

Educational leadership is a distinctive way of educational administration influencing or shaping people or education organization's goals, motivating behaviour towards the achievement of defined goals, and helping to express the group or organization's culture (Griffin, 2000; Shajahan & Shajahan, 2008). In other words, education leadership aims at the manner and approach of providing direction, implementation plans and motivating people.

Education leadership is usually the process and responsibility of school administrators and principals/heads of schools at different levels such as elementary, secondary, postsecondary, universities and the entire education system to involve stakeholders in creating positive image and changes in the education policy and learning. It plays a significant role in delivery of quality education which enables the learner to gain insight and understanding about life. It also focuses on the intellectual understanding of the world around him and enhances education development in terms of good performance in schools. Therefore, it can stimulate the process of industrialization and knowledge economy (Pont, Nusche, & Moorman, 2008).

Education leadership has become a priority in education policy agendas internationally. It plays a key role in improving school outcomes by influencing the motivation and capacities of teachers, as well as the school climate and environment. An effective education leadership is essential in improving the efficiency and equity of schooling. As countries are seeking to adapt their education systems to the needs of the contemporary society, expectations for schools and school leaders are changing (Winston, & Patterson, 2006). Many countries including Tanzania have moved towards decentralisation, making schools more autonomous in their decision making and holding them more accountable for the results. At the same time, the requirement to improve the overall student performance while serving more diverse student population is putting schools under pressure to use more evidence-based teaching practices instead of teaching as usual (Pont, Nusche, & Moorman, 2008).

Education leadership is an important aspect of any educational organisation, whether in the private or public sector is like what a central nervous system is to the human body in being an ingredient of industrialization and human capital development (Ankomah, Koomson, Bosu & Oduro, 2005). On the other hand, there is also increasing recognition that schools need education leadership if they want to reflect quality education and skills for individual and national prosperity in industrialization (Bush, 2007; UNESCO, 2014). In that matter education leadership in schools has a major role to play about making a difference in the lives of all learners regardless of their family background, socioeconomic status, race, gender, sexual orientation or geographical location. School leadership involves increasing the learning of all students as well as closing the 'gap' between groups of students.

Education leadership has a lot of advantages when used properly and at the right places. Fuller (1986) argued that when improvement of primary education is done as result of utilization of education leadership there is high possibility of spur economic development more sharply than other higher levels of schooling. Hanushek and Kimko (2000) showed that when education leadership is used to raise the academic performance and academic scores, there is high correlation with aggregated economic performance and positive growth rates of per capita income and Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Practically, education leadership reveals some indicators where it is exercised such as engaging pupils, teachers, parents and stakeholders in enhancing the pupils' learning process and school effectiveness. The ideal education leadership coordinates workflow contributes to higher level of job satisfaction and resolves technical difficulties rise in the school or institute. It believes more on engagement and integration of education stakeholders needed for maximization of the desired outcomes of education (Leithwood & Louis, 2012).

In order for education leadership to have impact in organizations or schools, education leaders should equip the stakeholders with appropriate knowledge and skills on education leadership, tools, equipment, and other resources so that the stakeholders can be successful in accomplishing the assigned tasks and responsibilities (Bandura, 1997). Research has shown that school leaders can make a difference in school and student performance if they are granted autonomy to make important decisions. However, autonomy alone does not automatically lead to improvement unless it is well supported. In addition, it is important that the core responsibilities of school leaders must be clearly defined and delimited. School leadership responsibilities should be defined through an understanding of the practices most likely to improve teaching and learning. Therefore, policy makers need to provide higher degree of autonomy with appropriate support. Greater degrees of autonomy should be coupled with new models of distributed leadership, new types of accountability and training and development for school leadership (Pont, Nusche, & Moorman, 2008).

Strong education leadership enhances human capital of the population and education system. This situation directly and indirectly impacts on the country and region in terms of economic growth and industrialization. Education leadership has the possibility of making both the individual receiving it and others better off. Specifically, a

more educated society may lead to higher rates of inventions; may make everybody more productive through the ability of firms to introduce new and better production methods; and may lead to more rapid introduction of new technologies. The link between educational leadership and industrialization stands on the ground of education system to reflect industrial development, produce people who are learnt, skilled and capable for industrialization. On the other hand, industrialization poses challenges which accelerate the need for workers with systematic education which requires systematic school organisation powered with education leadership. Therefore, in the absence of human capital and knowledge of technology, it is difficult to realise industrialization and knowledge economy (Hanusheki, 2005).

3. Industrialization

Industrialization is the process by which traditionally non-industrial sectors such as agriculture, education and the health of an economy become increasingly similar to the manufacturing, the production and service sector of the economy such as the production industries, service industries and tourism. In other words, industrialization is a generic name for a set of economic and social processes related to the discovery of more efficient ways for the creation of value in the primary sector of economic activities referring to agriculture, hunting, fishing, and resource extraction, and the tertiary sector referring to services (Simandan, 2009). The history of industrialization began in 18th century during industrial revolution when agrarian activities started using machines in large scale production instead of hand-made tools. The inventions permanently changed the society in terms of culture and demography.

Today the term 'industrialization' is used to describe the development of industry. However, it is multifaceted, because industry can be defined in a number of ways. Firstly, industry can be defined as the production of material goods, excluding agriculture. Secondly, industry can be defined as being made up of the mining, energy and manufacturing sectors. This classification of industry is defined in terms of the kind of output, not how the goods are made. The third definition they offer, however, concerns how the goods are made and focuses on the production process and sees industry as a particular way of organizing production (Hanusheki, 2005).

From a variety of definitions and concepts, industrialization seems to be a process, not an event. A process is an emergent property of a system resulting from a collection of events that share a number of similarities and that unfold over a slower timescale. If one entrepreneur today opens an industrial plant in an otherwise agrarian region, that singular event cannot be labelled as industrialization. If a collection of events of this same kind achieves sufficient significance for the local economy, scholars and policymakers alike are entitled to refer to it at a higher level of generalization. That is what, they can speak of a process of industrialization changing the face of that regional economy. Therefore, the concept 'industrialization' should be restricted to the qualitative economic change occurring whenever an agrarian economy becomes to such an extent affected by the opening of new industrial plants (Simandan, 2009).

Many of the countries that industrialized successfully in the nineteenth century first acquired technology through imports, then rapidly moved to producing manufactures for export. There were policies that allowed opportunities on foreign markets to be communicated to domestic producers, that allowed domestic resources to move freely in response to the opportunities, and that complemented the existing resources through education, training, and infrastructure all contributed to the success (World Bank, 1987). One of the better-known aspects of the nineteenth century industrialization was the importance of transportation and communication networks. Transportation and communication networks integrated and expanded domestic markets and increased their efficiency, for example railways, roads and marine. They also integrated domestic markets into the global economy, making it easier for exporters to compete. But transportation and communications networks are capital intensive, and therefore expensive, especially during early stages of industrialization. Governments of countries industrialized in the nineteenth century helped to finance the construction of transportation and communication networks directly or indirectly (World Bank, 1987).

Education, skills formation, and technological adaptation was the means of transition from a primarily agricultural and trading economy to an industrial economy which required, at least in the initial stages, an increase in the skills of the labour force. To use foreign technology effectively, producers had a choice to examine the availability, make intelligent selections, and adapt them to local conditions. All of this calls for education. More than general education is required whether science, technical education or social science (World Bank, 1987). In addition, its government established a system of financial support for research in universities. Private industry also maintained research laboratories that sometimes received public support. Although some of these laboratories conducted original research, one of their main tasks has been to spot innovations elsewhere and provide the expertise that makes rapid imitation possible (World Bank, 1987).

Due to importance of industrialization in the overall GDP and productivity in 2015, the world leaders agreed to build resilient infrastructure, promote sustainable industrialization and foster innovation. The agreement later became Sustainable Development Goal #9 – *“Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation”* (ADB, 2018). The focus was to comprise the technology sector, the sector responsible for the introduction of innovation; to process the large-scale introduction of manufacturing, advanced technical enterprises, and other productive economic activity into an area, society and country; to base on factory production, division of labour, concentration of industries and population in certain geographical areas, and urbanization (ADB, 2018).

Many of the African countries including Tanzania have realized the importance of industrialization. Hence, they began to design education systems which reflect industrial development and industrialization. Africa happened to have a large population, and natural resources influenced to step on early stages of industrialization. According to Worldometer website, Africa has the population of 1.29 billion, which is a large market next to India and China in world market. The governments’ domestic and foreign policies

which allowed producers and factors of production to respond to incentives have been a crucial progress along the path towards industrialization (World Bank, 1987). In Africa, industrialization promises to address the promotion of economic diversification, inclusive growth, efficient utilisation of abundant physical, mineral and human resources and in the process eliminate poverty and hence structurally transform. Meanwhile, industrialization continues to play a major role in Africa's economic growth performance, and it has the potential to promote trade-induced industrialization of the continent provided it is deliberately directed at industrialization. For this purpose, trade policy must be consciously designed, effectively implemented and managed with regular monitoring and evaluation. Such a policy must recognise any key developments in the global production system especially internationalization of the production system with a view to promoting value addition through processing and manufacturing. Finally, the goal of trade-induced industrialization must also guide the conduct, negotiations and implementation of trade and investment agreements and arrangements (UNECA, 2015). Despite the industrialization progress in Africa, there are challenges which hinder its development. They are named as: (i) low investment in industrial development; (ii) poor infrastructure services, resulting in higher production and transaction costs; (iii) high sovereign risk, poor governance and weak institutions; (iv) ill-advised industrial policies; and (v) generally rigid macro-economic frameworks (UNECA, 2007). In addition to that, Africa is facing the challenge of small size and ethnic fragmentation of many countries that too often result in internal conflict, due to the geographical nature of many landlocked resource-scarce states (Sandrey, & Edinger, 2011).

In Tanzania, there is a long history of industrialization since 1970's when Tanzania established so many industries. The situation of industrialization provided employment for school and college graduates. The story changed between 1980's and 1990's when the country enforced implemented the World Bank and IMF policy of SAP (Structural Adjustment Programme) on industries. Most of the industries established before gradually began to collapse for so many reasons including economic crisis after the Kagera war between 1978 and 1980. The only solution found was to privatize most of the public industries. As a result, so many industries were privatized but never produced like before. Some industries under private sector changed to warehouses and other machines were just dismantled and sold like scrapheap.

In 1995, the government being aware of the significance of industrialization appointed a group of experts to formulate a policy document to that effect in consultation with the different sections of the Tanzanian community at large. The outcome was the Tanzania Development Vision 2025. The vision aims to guide Tanzania's development effort into the 21st Century and achieve a diversified and semi-industrialized economy with a substantial industrial sector comparable to typical middle-income countries and to cope with the infrastructure requirements for the vision in all sectors by the year 2025 (Planning Commission, 1995).

Before any evaluation, in 2005, the government came up with the Tanzania Mini – Tiger plan 2020 to fast-track the implementation of vision 2025 by adopting the Asia Tiger model. This came six years after the vision document was seemingly dumped in selves.

The mini – Tiger plan that led to introduction of Special Economic Zones (SEZ) and Export Processing Zones (EPZ) which have been implemented with mixed outcome (Planning Commission, 1995). Later, the Long-Term Perspective Plan (LTPP) 2011/12 – 2025/26 was another plan developed to help the implementation of vision 2025. The LTPP has been divided into three 5-year plans to simplify its execution. The five-year development plan (FYDP) I 2011/12 – 2015/16 was meant to focus on building the requisite infrastructure and improve energy supply and markets. The FYDP II 2016/17 – 2020/21 intended to deepen industrialization as the key pillar of social economic and political development. FYDP III 2021/22 – 2025/26 will focus on further promoting the competitiveness of the manufacturing sector and substantial improvement in Tanzania’s share in global and regional trade (Planning Commission, 1995).

In 2003, the National Trade Policy was developed by the Ministry of Industry and Trade observing the principles stated in vision 2025 by emphasizing the private sector to lead the export sector. The policy insisted stimulation and encouraged value addition as one of its main objectives. The policies mentioned above are so many to be implemented considering availability of resources in Tanzania. Some of those policies were weak and others were strong, but the major challenge was poor implementation. That resulted in failure to keep pace with the wind of industrialization in the world. In Tanzania, there is a popular slogan “*Nchi ya viwanda*” which means Tanzania the industrial country, therefore prioritizes industrialization (Mufuruki, Mawji, Kasiga, & Marwa, 2017). But without implementation of the strategies, the actual industrialization in Tanzania will face challenges.

4. Knowledge economy

The knowledge economy is essentially an economy whose development is based on ‘the ability to create and use of knowledge and, therefore, transforming information of all kinds concerning innovation to support the development of distinctive and competitive businesses (World Bank, 2006).

The pioneer of Knowledge Economy, the World Bank, defines knowledge economy as the economy which is built on creation, dissemination and acquisition of knowledge to sustain economic growth and competitiveness (World Bank, 2006). Moreover, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), which is the group of 34 member countries that discuss and develop economic and social policy and support free market economy, defines knowledge economy as that directly based on production, distribution and use of knowledge and information (OECD, 1996). Both definitions agree that knowledge economy has to do with the production, distribution and use of knowledge as the main sources of the economy. Briefly, knowledge economy is about producing and selling as well as buying and using knowledge with common elements of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and innovation education. The knowledge economy is also seen as the latest stage of development in global economic restructuring from an agricultural economy to industrial economy based on technology and human capital, business product, educational, innovative and

intellectual products and services that can be exported for a high value return (Julien, 2007).

Production and services based on knowledge economy and intensive activities contribute to an accelerated pace of technical and scientific advancement because the key components of a knowledge economy more rely on intellectual capabilities than on physical inputs or natural resources. This stage that relies on intellectual capabilities has been marked by the upheavals in technological innovations and the globally competitive need for innovation with new products and processes that develop from research and development (R&D). In the knowledge economy, the specialized labour force is characterized as computer literate and well-trained in handling data, developing algorithms and simulated models, and innovating on processes and systems (Julien, 2007). In fact, knowledge economy increasingly engages immaterial investment economy such as training and research rather than traditional investment in which natural resources, equipment and infrastructures are used.

Worldwide examples of the knowledge economy taking place among many others countries include the Silicon Valley in California (which serves as the global centre for high technology, innovation and social media in America); biotechnology in Hyderabad, India in Asia; electronics and digital media in Seoul, South Korea; ICT hub in Rwanda in East Africa, just to mention a few. Many other cities and regions try to follow a knowledge-driven development paradigm and increase their knowledge base by investing in higher education and research institutions in order to attract high skilled labour and better positioning themselves in the global competition. Yet, despite the digital tools democratising access to knowledge, research shows that knowledge economy activities remain as concentrated as ever in traditional economic cores (World Bank, 2006).

The development of the knowledge economy has changed the labour market demands for competencies and skills. There is evidence that upskilling has increased in demand for skills and partly in response to rising educational attainments in the population. The forces at play suggest that further increases in the overall levels of education are needed. Therefore, higher levels of education which are nurtured by good education leadership is needed not only just to prepare better knowledge workers but also to improve the likelihood of participation in further learning throughout adult life, and reduce the chances of long-term unemployment and marginalisation in world economy. At the same time, many organizations have argued that new or additional competencies and skills are required from workers. On the basis of the evidence available in general trends in competences and on their relation to the knowledge economy, no doubt that high levels of education and literacy are the key principal competencies demanded in the knowledge economy (OECD, 2001).

Education leadership basically provides quality education with products of competent workers with the core academic and cognitive competences required to participate most effectively. These core competences provide the base to facilitate further training and further upgrading of those specific technical skills required for knowledge economy workers who require the production with high levels of competences and skills.

To some extent, knowledge economy workers have acquired and are applying relevant, advanced levels of skills not developed through formal education only but through interaction with the world economy and knowledge. Other competences although not necessarily new are now seen to be more important for knowledge economy workers. For example, team-work, communication skills, business management, personal skills and problem solving skills are now very important. Those skills have been associated with new organisation practices knowledge economy. The skills are not seen as substitutes for education and literacy skills, but rather as complementary to them.

It has been determined that successful transition to the knowledge economy often includes four elements: long-term investment in education, the development of innovation capability, the modernization of the information infrastructure and the creation of a conducive economic environment. The World Bank has set these elements as the four pillars of the knowledge economy within the Knowledge Economy Framework.

These pillars are as follows:

- An economic incentive and institutional regime that provides good economic policies and institutions that permit efficient mobilization and allocation of resources and stimulating creativity and incentives for the efficient creation, dissemination and use of existing knowledge;
- Educated and skilled workers who can continuously upgrade and adapt their skills to efficiently create and use knowledge;
- An effective innovation system of firms, research centres, universities, consultants and other organizations that can keep up with the knowledge revolution, tap into the growing stock of global knowledge and assimilate and adapt it to the local needs;
- A modern and adequate information infrastructure that can facilitate effective communication, dissemination and processing of information and knowledge (Tocan, 2012).

Significant aspects of the knowledge economy growth are policy environment and investment climate as they emphasize public and private trainings to the workers. Both make a contribution to the knowledge economy. While the private sector has had considerable success in providing appropriate training in urban areas to larger businesses with specific needs, the public sector addresses broader education content and often offers better support in isolated or rural areas although training benefits are greatest where the investment climates are strong. The implication is that both public and private training merit expansion, attention and increasing interconnection in an overall strategy (OECD, 1996).

Some of the most obvious connections between lifelong learning and the knowledge economy are to be found in the provision of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) (OECD, 1996). According to OECD, successful knowledge economies rely on four sources of innovation skills:

- Scientific and technical knowledge;
- Interactions and incentives to innovate among users and doers; and

- Decentralized modular patterns of innovation within a coordinated system;
- Widespread application of information and communication technologies, including in education (OECD, 2001).

In most cases, the greatest challenges of knowledge and skills development is to find ways to promote the transferability of learning and what is learned from informal to formal economy. (OECD, 1996). In reality, the knowledge economy needs a favourable business environment that is governed by the rule of law, supported by government free of corruption. As part of the knowledge economy initiative, there are other issues related that should not be left behind such as improving telecoms regulation and developing ecosystems that allow venture capital and private equity firms to grow.

This paper suggests that, while further increases in the levels of education are needed, for knowledge economy workers and others, also a wide range of competences including working skills competences of teamwork, communication skills and problem-solving skills are needed (OECD, 2001). We should bear in mind that knowledge economy is important as it is export intensive, high productivity that generates stable employment and income (or wealth) from abroad. It is an element of the economy in which companies invest heavily in both their employees and physical capital in order to maintain their competitive edge (Tocan, 2012). The results are more and better-quality goods productivity and services while consuming fewer natural resources and enabling more efficient use of human resources. This is particularly important in Tanzania which over-relies on natural resources which are impermanent and at the same time harness the power of technology and embrace innovation (Clarke, 2001). In Tanzania, knowledge economy is reflected more in tourism service industry than in other sectors compared. Now, it is the right time to focus on other sectors and industries as well.

5. Conclusion

Based on the discussion raised on this topic, there is close connectedness among the three key words: education leadership, industrialization and knowledge economy. The one leads is education leadership which normally guides and shapes the education system from the school level to the ministry. At the same time, it engages education stakeholders in opportunities and challenges facing the education system. Through successful educational leadership, quality education is the end result. Quality education imparts the beneficiaries with different and useful skills used in jobs and life. These skills lead to innovation and production of quality goods and services. The products and services are normally sold internally, and some are exported to earn foreign exchange. In other words, knowledge economy is the key factor in the exportation of goods and services and generating stable employment and income or wealth from abroad. In combination with three factors – education leadership, industrialization and knowledge economy. The outcome is the country's sustainable prosperity and development.

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